

SteamDry

D8.1 SteamDry IT concept

Christoph Nölle, Alexander Dunayvitser and

Andreas Wolff, BFI

Roope Siilasto and Janne Keränen, VTT

Floor Boon, WR

Reinhard Jentsch, AIT

Ana Arias Calvo, USC

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The SteamDry project will develop and pilot superheated steam drying technologies for web-like materials such as paper, board, tissue, and nonwovens, aiming at a significant reduction in the CO₂ footprint of the paper and pulp industry. As part of this endeavour, a set of simulation models for various parts of the drying process will be developed, and advanced control concepts will be implemented and tested in a set of laboratory-scale piloting trials.

The present document lays down the preliminary IT concept for the modelling activities, the automation and control approach, and the monitoring and evaluation of the lab trials. Furthermore, it provides a selected overview of similar IT concepts from past European research projects and other relevant standardisation activities, thus establishing the state of the art as a basis for the SteamDry project.

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AUTHORS

Name	Organisation
Christoph Nölle	BFI
Alexander Dunayvitser	BFI
Andreas Wolff	BFI
Roope Siilasto	VTT
Janne Keränen	VTT
Reinhard Jentsch	AIT
Floor Boon	WR
Ana Arias Calvo	USC

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1 Introduction

In the evolving field of industrial drying technologies, particularly within the paper and pulp industry, the need for enhanced efficiency, reduced energy consumption, and improved product quality has never been greater. The SteamDry project is a comprehensive effort aimed at revolutionizing drying processes through the implementation of superheated steam drying (SSD).

This document describes an Information Technology Concept (IT-Concept) needed to reach the project goals. Following this introduction, an overview of the modelling activities planned in the project is given. Modelling builds the basis for technological decisions within the project and will also be used to optimize energy consumption within the drying process.

The third chapter describes the pilot plant at VTT that will be used for trials and is the basis for process modelling and optimization. The Pilot plant will be used to showcase the developed drying technology and to test and implement optimization strategies.

The fourth chapter delves into the state of the art of Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) platforms and also describes pulp and paper industry-specific automation aspects.

The sixth chapter is dedicated to the actual IT-Concept developed within the project. It includes creating the necessary IT-Infrastructure to host a digital twin of the pilot plant as well as to run optimization algorithms. Since the project is just at the beginning, it is still unclear if the concept has to be modified at a later stage.

2 SteamDry Modelling activities

2.1 Overview

The development of energy-efficient drying technology in SteamDry includes the development of a set of simulation and control models. The starting point will be a simple static model of the drying process based on energy and mass balance, used for the initial specification of the drying technology, which will later be enhanced to a dynamic system model covering also other relevant equipment, such as a cleaner and heat exchanger. While the initial models will be developed as standalone components, their integration into a comprehensive digital twin platform capable of online operation is foreseen in a second step.

These digital twins will be based on both synthetic data from the standalone models and actual process data from laboratory trials conducted in the project. An innovative control algorithm for multi-objective process optimization will be developed on top of the digital twin platform.

Figure 1 presents an overview of models related to the digital twin development and control, showing the individual models and their dependencies, and also the main data sources used.

Figure 1. SteamDry modelling activities pertaining to digital twins and the control concept. For each activity, the end month, project task and the responsible partner are indicated in the last row.

Regarding the fouling problem, i.e., the contamination of the steam with fibers and other pollutants, a dedicated optimization and scheduling algorithm for the steam cleaning process is foreseen. It will be based on a fouling model and incorporate an anomaly detection mechanism, see Figure 2.

Figure 2. SteamDry modelling activities pertaining to steam fouling and cleaning scheduling.

In addition, a task is foreseen for the environmental and economic assessment of the developed technology, which will also include the development of a simulation model.

2.2 Individual models

2.2.1 Static dryer models for convective and contact dryers (Task 3.2, AIT)

The static dryer model purpose is comparing process layouts, finding favourable process condition for the SSD and consider electrification issues, while providing mass and energy flows and performance indicators of the overall system. It will consider convective and

contact SSD dryers. The model will later be verified with data from pilot experiments. The simplified model is the basis for more detailed process and scale-up models in the following tasks. It is a steady-state model built and simulated in IPSEpro using a Newton-Solver. IPSEpro is a proprietary equation-based process simulation tool with a graphical flow-sheet editor. The model is based on mass and energy balances and efficiency relations.

The model is not intended to be part of online simulation, data processing or direct data exchange and model coupling with other models. Although interfacing via C/C++ is in principle possible. Information is collected for the following modelling task. Data input and output are intended via GUI or Excel-Plugin.

The simulation activities at VTT include i) steady-state models for conductive and convective dryers using superheated steam (done in T3.2, tools: KuiSim and Balas) and ii) plant-wide process concept model(s) for the integration of the superheated steam dryer to an existing paper mill (done in T4.1, tool: Balas).

Balas is a steady-state simulation software developed at VTT with emphasis on pulp and paper mills. It contains an extensive selection of unit operation modules for fibre processing and web drying. With Balas, site-wide material and energy balances can be calculated, heat recovery and heat integration analyses can be performed and process optimisation and fitting process model to be measured can be conducted. It contains an easy MS Excel interface that enables the import and export of any process parameter. The Balas-Excel interphase provides good visualisation tools of process data, tailored report sheets and clear representation of balances and process parameters to guarantee smooth information transfer.

More detailed drying simulations can be done with KuiSim and PaperNova which are VTT's inhouse drying simulators. The drying models of KuiSim and PaperNova are run off-line and fitted with measured data. The equations describing the drying phenomenon in PaperNova have been implemented in three unit operation modules used in Balas to model the drying section of a paper machine in detail. The possible drying section configurations in use today can consist of conventional double or single tier, combined cylinder and through fabric impingement or combined vacuum roll and direct impingement drying.

2.2.2 Dynamic system simulation model (Task 4.2, AIT)

The purpose of the dynamic system simulation model is the dynamic simulation of the SSD process pilot plant. The model is built and simulated with the modelling language Modelica in the modelling and simulation environment Dymola as a differential algebraic equation system (DAE). The model consists of the SSD dryer, the heat recovery components, such as compressors, heat exchangers and the cleaning equipment. It is modelled by mass and energy balances, fluid property data and first principles and empirical correlation for heat and mass transfer. This is done in close cooperation with VTT, VAL and PIL to include their experience, modelling results and equipment performance data.

The model is used to evaluate different scenarios for the process layout and the heat recovery components to maximize energy efficiency. It will also be used to guide the planning and evaluation of pilot plant experiments, considering technical and safety requirements relevant to dynamic operation. The model will be refined and validated with experimental data. It is also intended to provide synthetic training data for the digital

twin and digital agent application, especially of SSD process parts that are not realized in the pilot plant.

Those simulation tasks are foremost intended as offline simulations, with time series data files as input and output. Although the model and simulation environment are – in principle – capable of real-time simulation and several interfacing options. Those comprise the Functional Mockup Interface (FMI), C/C++, FORTRAN and in terms of networking DDE and MQTT.

2.2.3 Advanced drying models (Tasks 6.1-6.4, WR)

A dynamic physical model of the dryer will be made describing

- (i) the drying of the paper (moisture content and temperature of the paper sheet as a function of paper depth and time),
- (ii) the influence of non-condensable like air on the drying process and
- (iii) the possible release of contaminants like fibers.

The drying of the paper and the influence of air on the drying process will be based on conventional state-of-the-art drying models with heat and moisture transport in the paper sheet and extended to superheated steam conditions with the inclusion of air (and other non-condensable). The acceptable amount of air leakage into the dryer will be quantified.

The possible release of fibres will be based on fibre-fibre interaction (i.e. bonding) and how this interaction is influenced under superheated steam conditions during drying (e.g. shrinkage, collapse of fibres via loss of intracellular water). Moreover, the fiber-scale model will interact with the volume-averaged (macroscopic) model between the steam flow (shear) and paper web structure.

The dynamic physical model of the dryer will be integrated in the dynamic models (WP5, WP8). The model will be verified with experimental data from T6.4.

2.2.4 Fouling model (Tasks 7.1-7.2, UT)

A fouling model will be developed that captures the fouling of the superheated steam by fibres, air, and other relevant pollutants. The hybrid fouling model is partly based on first principles (mass and energy balances) and the more complex phenomena of fouling can be modelled with surrogate models that are trained with experimental data.

2.2.5 Cleaning optimization and scheduling (Tasks 7.3-7.4, UT)

Fouling models can be used to optimize the operational strategy of a production cycle, but it is evident that over multiple of such production cycles a cleaning procedure is required. A cleaning model will be developed that describes in a qualitative way how cleaning settings affect cleaning effectiveness. The fouling and cleaning model are coupled and an optimization algorithm will be used to schedule the number and the length of the fouling-cleaning cycles over longer time horizons. This will lead to a set point trajectory for the operational settings which will feed the control system.

2.2.6 Digital Twins (Task 8.3, BFI)

Digital twins will be developed for all relevant equipment, such as dryers, compressors, steam cleaners and auxiliary units, which integrate the standalone models developed before (see Sections 2.2.1 to 2.2.5 above). Mostly, they will be implemented as surrogate models trained on synthetic data from the base models, and also on actual process

data, if possible. The goal is to enable the near real-time operation of the simulation models. Several methods for KPI calculations will be integrated into the digital twins to be used for the model validation and the validation of the project results. An HMI will be developed and implemented to be able to administrate the whole system, to setup some parameters and to visualise the digital twins as well as data and results.

2.2.7 Cross-process automation and energy management system (Task 8.4, BFI)

Three subsystems are being developed to optimize the overall system:

- 1.) A safe and efficient reinforcement learning based moisture control system, e.g. by means of Bayesian optimisation, process data and digital twins of the drying process.
- 2.) A model and data driven safe reinforcement learning energy management system that reduces the energy consumption of the whole system while maintaining the quality of the product.
- 3.) An economic energy dispatching system to utilise the recovered energy using dryers and evaporators, district heating of community, utilization of heat pumps, conversion to electricity etc.

Finally, to coordinate the three control and optimisation tasks, a consensus strategy is developed by considering the developed control system as an agent. This leads to an overall distributed system. Components can be added or removed as needed. During the pilot tests, the automation will be applied in the VTT demonstration plant.

2.2.8 Anomalies detection and countermeasures (Task 8.5, BFI)

A data and/or model-driven AI based anomaly detection system for paper mills will be developed, e.g. for early detection of fouling in the heat exchanger and triggering of countermeasures. For this purpose, concepts like classical model fault detection combined with AI based residual classification or pure data-driven AI methods like UMAP projection, digital twins that describe the fouling process. In the first step, the detection method and countermeasures will be developed and tested in the simulation environment. Process data from the pilot plant and an industrial plant will be used. The method is implemented and tested on the automation system of the test facility in the second step. Finally, the implementation and testing of the procedures will be on an actual industrial plant.

2.2.9 Data exchange and process modelling (Task 10.1, USC)

In order to assess the feasibility of implementing the technology on a larger scale, process modelling will be developed using commercial tools, such as SuperPro Designer® or BALAS software®, based on laboratory data and scaled up to a facility capacity analogous to that of traditional air dryer system from WP3,4 and 5. Besides, also literature revision is going to be made looking to identify alternative drying technologies in order to analyze the advantages and challenges with respect to steam drying technology. And, if required, also literature will be used for gathering all the required data for the modelling. To this end, this process modelling is going to consider all the expected inputs for the drying system of the different raw materials, in order to evaluate which is the affections of changing the input stream in the SSD technology.

In this way, it is possible to get all the mass and energy balances necessary to obtain the data for the life cycle inventory, including input and output flows related to the process,

which are required for the development of the environmental and economic assessment of Task 10.2 and Task 10.3.

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for SSD technology will be conducted in accordance with ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards. This involves four key phases:

1. Defining the goal and scope of the assessment, which in this case is to analyze the environmental profile of SSD technology.
2. Constructing the life cycle inventory, using modelling data to account for all environmental loads.
3. Assessing the impact, utilizing the Ecolinvent database and SimaPro software® to evaluate environmental impacts.
4. Interpreting the results, which includes analyzing the impact loads to understand their causes and proposing alternative scenarios that could lead to better environmental scores.

On the other hand, also an economic assessment is going to be developed, looking to analyze the economic viability and feasibility of the SSD technology. For this, a techno-economic analysis is going to be performed, considering the scoring of the capital and operational expenditures, and the most common financial metrics, such as the net present value, payback, and internal rate of return, among others. Moreover, also, if possible, a comparison with other drying technologies is going to be performed for this economic perspective, looking to identify its potentialities.

3 SteamDry Pilot Plant

The location of the superheated steam Pilot will be in VTT Jyväskylä piloting plant, where it will be installed after selection to either Sampo or cylinder dryer pilot lines. The pilot line pictures are shown in Figures 3 and 4. Cylinder dryer pilot represents the conventional drying concept in the paper industry, but it differs in not having any hood around it. Sampo pilot line has three drying concepts: Impingement, through air and steel belt drying available. Selection will be done by the end of M15.

Figure 3. VTT's cylinder dryer pilot line located at Jyväskylä, Finland.

Figure 4. VTT's Sampo pilot line drying section, located in Jyväskylä, Finland.

3.1 Plant overview

Test equipment is controlled and adjusted at two operating stations from the control room, see Figure 5. The control room has a printer for printing screens and an engineering station for programming the automation system. The control room has an equipment cabinet containing process stations as well as the necessary fibre optic, ethernet and Profibus connections. The automation system is decentralised, so I/O cabinets with I/O cards for measuring and controlling the test equipment are placed outside of it. I/O cabinets are connected via ethernet to process stations. Some of the valves and measurements are connected to the automation system by Profibus field bus.

Figure 5. System layout of piloting plant

Frequency converters and a User Management Component (UMC) system for controlling electric motors have been placed in the electrical room. The drives and UMC motor units are connected to the automation system via Profibus bus.

An OPC server is located in the computer room for storing and processing measurement data. An additional operating station has been located also for the control and adjustment of the second hall's piloting equipment. The electrical room of the piloting hall houses a process station and I/O cards, as well as the necessary fiber optic, ethernet and Profibus connections.

3.2 Process data

Data measured from the system includes air and web temperature and conditions, web speed and moisture and power levels. The process data measuring rate is 1 Hz. There are more than 600 measuring point data collected from the trials all the time. Figures 6-8 show pilot lines drying process layouts. Time series data is stored in the analysis software Wedge¹. Wedge is a data analysis tool used in the process industry. It's designed to improve industrial plant efficiency by providing fast online process data analytics. The tool is capable of digesting all the process data, from multiple sources, for analysis and diagnosis. Wedge has several features including: 1) Data Mining & Root Cause Analysis: It uncovers and suggests possible root causes and consequences of process events before they escalate into big problems, 2) Data Visualization: It allows you to integrate process and quality data flow from all data sources, build your own process diagrams and dashboard, and view, synthesize, and analyse data in seconds, 3) Data Cleansing: It provides tools for data cleansing and focusing, as well as dynamic process delay compensation and 4) Advanced Analysis & Diagnostics: It offers advanced analysis tools that enable you to identify relationships among measurements, trace the source or consequence of abnormal process behaviour, and predict and avoid process disturbances. Several different data sources can be utilized in the Wedge process

¹ <https://wedge.trimble.com/>

diagnostics system. The most common databases used in connection with process control systems, such as Valmet DNA, Honeywell PHD and Microsoft's SQL database are supported. The analysis tools provided by Wedge can be used by these external historical databases, so-called direct data sources. In addition to the Wedge server data can be retrieved from the saved ASCII files into the Wedge system for analysis. In this case, a separate SQL database is created on the server from the ASCII file, which is used as a data source. In addition, the so-called remote data source, which means DAS server data sources located in another Wedge system. Collection of process data in the pilot is done to the WDB database (Wedge Data Base) that comes with the system. It collects data from the Valmet DNA via OPC server.

Figure 6. Layout of process of cylinder dryer pilot.

Figure 7. Layout of process of Sampo impingement and steel belt dryer pilot.

Figure 8. Layout of process of Sampo through air dryer pilot

3.3 Product data

From the product, surface temperature, and moisture are measured on-line and several other supporting product quality measurements are made in laboratory. This can be done for both pilots.

3.4 Data transfer possibilities

Data transfer in the system is via OPC server. Data transfer to system is typically made by operator, later developed to be accepted by operator and in the end of the project some process control input -data can even be automatic.

4 Industrial IoT platforms

4.1 Overview

IoT platforms provide a modern approach for managing operational technology. They enable device connectivity, data integration, application programming interfaces, access control, etc. In the SteamDry project, an IoT platform will be used for collecting process data and model results, provide a runtime environment for simulation and control algorithms, and enable process monitoring via a user interface. It will hence be an essential tool for the evaluation of the drying trials.

4.2 Standardisation and technologies

In the following sub-sections several key constituents of an IoT platform are briefly introduced along with relevant standardisation activities, technological developments, and open-source software components. The first sub-section 4.2.1 deals with the overall enterprise architecture, the following ones with more specific subcomponents.

4.2.1 Automation architecture & enterprise integration

The IEC62264/ISA95 functional model

The classical automation architecture follows the functional model of the standard IEC62264, based on the earlier ISA95, which is commonly referred to as the automation pyramid (Figure 3). It describes a hierarchical interplay of components, starting from the physical process and sensors and actuators installed at level 0, via programmable logic controllers (PLCs) at level 1, “control room” integration at level 2, the manufacturing execution system (MES) at level 3, to the enterprise-wide systems at level 4. There is a flow of information between the levels, but usually data is aggregated as it moves from the bottom to the top. For instance, raw sensor data may be collected by the PLC at level 1 in 1 kHz resolution, recorded in the level 2 system at 1 s resolution, at the level 3 system at 1 min resolution, and the level 4 systems may receive only hourly or daily average values.

Figure 9. Automation pyramid (from Katti, B.. *Ontology-Based Approach to Decentralized Production Control in the Context of Cloud Manufacturing Execution Systems*, doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.11486.46402).

The (Industrial) Internet of Things paradigm

The (Industrial) Internet of Things (IoT/IIoT) (Figure 10) represents a move away from the hierarchical structure towards a more integrated system, where all relevant sensors, actors and software systems are directly connected, either to a central platform or in a decentral way. It is characterised by ubiquitous connectivity via internet protocols, instead of reliance on fieldbus protocols at the lower levels, and convergence of operational technology (OT) and information technology (IT) in general.

Figure 10. The internet of things (from RAMI 4.0).

A reference architecture for the industrial internet has been published by the Industrial Internet Consortium, the Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (IIRA), see Figure 11. It contains multiple viewpoints, from Business via Usage and Function to Implementation. A possible realization of the implementation view proposed in IIRA is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 11. Viewpoints in the Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (IIRA) (from IIRA, v.1.10).

Figure 12. IIRA Implementation view: mapping between a three-tier architecture to the functional domains (from IIRA).

Another reference architecture is called RAMI 4.0 (Reference Architectural Model Industrie 4.0). It integrates the hierarchy levels of IEC62264 and adds two additional dimensions, the product life cycle dimension and the architecture dimension, as shown in Figure 13.

The FIWARE initiative has also published a Smart Industry Reference Architecture, see Figure 14. It is more concrete than the two reference architectures introduced above, however, and could probably be viewed as a realization of the implementation view of the IIRA.

Figure 13. RAMI 4.0 reference architecture (from RAMI 4.0).

Figure 14. FIWARE Smart Industry Reference Architecture

4.2.2 Device connectivity

The basis for IoT applications is the connectivity of sensors and actors to higher-level IT systems. Historically, a wide range of transport technologies and protocols has been used

for this purpose, but more recently a convergence towards internet technologies based on the TCP/UDP/IP transport protocols has taken place. Typical protocols of relevance in the industrial setting are OPC-UA, Modbus, or MQTT.

For the SteamDry project most device data will be retrieved from a higher-level system (Level 2 or Level 3 in the terminology of the automation pyramid, see Figure 9), therefore device-level protocols are not a direct concern.

4.2.3 Storage

The storage layer is responsible for storing data. The classical technologies used for this purpose are databases, most prominently relational databases such as OracleDB, PostgreSQL or MS SQL Server, which are well-suited for storing large amounts of structured data in a tabular format (row-based). So-called NoSQL databases replace the relational model by other paradigms, such as key-value stores or document-centric storage.

With more diverse types of data being used in modern IoT applications, the need for other specialized storage solutions arose. Large amounts of unstructured data, such as images and videos, are often stored in object storage instead of file hierarchies. Object storage is an essential ingredient of so-called data lakes, which provide a centralized storage layer for all kinds of structured and unstructured raw data. Since conventional data lakes do not impose schema constraints on the data, they allow for fast integration of new data sources. On the other hand, this flexibility can hamper the useability of the data. Ill-maintained data lakes are sometimes called data swamps, for this reason. As a compromise, additional tools are often used on top of the data lake itself to enable more convenient data extraction and improve interoperability. These include metadata repositories and SQL overlays, such as Presto/Trino or Apache Iceberg.

An important class of data in the IoT context is timeseries data, generated for instance by sensor measurements. Timeseries data has some characteristics that make it ill-suited for traditional SQL databases, such as the large amount of data generated over time, different access characteristics for recent vs. older data, and certain common aggregation and access patterns. Dedicated timeseries databases have been developed in response to these challenges. They are typically based on columnar data storage, allowing for very fast access and efficient compression of individual series data. Popular timeseries databases include InfluxDB, TimescaleDB, and KairosDB.

Historically, the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) used to be a popular solution for storing large amounts data, which has mostly been superseded by cloud object storage.

A popular file format for the exchange of smaller amounts of IoT data is the comma separated value text file (CSV file). Its biggest advantage is the human readability of its content and ubiquitous support by parsing tools. Due to the text encoding it represents a rather inefficient storage format, however. In recent years, the Apache Parquet file format has emerged as a standardized binary format for columnar data, which has reached widespread support. There are even databases which have migrated to Parquet as underlying storage format, most notably InfluxDB (for timeseries data) and Delta Lake.

Whereas the technologies discussed above, such as databases and data lakes, are typically used within a single enterprise, data sharing between companies within the value chain has become a more pressing need for many applications. This comes with additional requirements pertaining to security, governance, trust, etc. The data spaces concept has been introduced to describe an integrated approach to these issues.

Industry initiatives working on data spaces include the International data spaces association (IDSA)², Gaia-X³ and the Big data value association (BDVA)⁴. Figure 15 shows the BDVA data spaces reference architecture.

Figure 15. BDVA data spaces architecture (from BDVA: DATA SHARING SPACES AND INTEROPERABILITY, '23)

4.2.4 Application Programming Interfaces (APIs)

While it is possible for applications to access data directly from the storage layer, this is considered bad practice, since it introduces a strong coupling and thus significantly impedes later schema evolution or other changes to the storage layer. Instead, appropriate application programming interfaces (APIs) should be defined, through which applications exclusively access the storage layer.

Typically, data residing in different storage technologies will be served by different APIs, as well. For instance, timeseries data, relational data, and images might all be served via dedicated APIs.

The standard technology for APIs is HTTP with JSON-formatted payloads (REST interfaces). Some drawbacks of this technology are the lack of bi-directional communication options and suboptimal payload sizes. Traditionally, bi-directional communication has been implemented by means of polling approaches, which does not scale very well, however. Nowadays, the websockets protocol is a widely supported extension of HTTP for bi-directional communication, which is even available in web browsers. The lambda architecture emphasizes the stream processing of incoming data as a first-class citizen in the big data processing architecture. It is often realized in terms of an MQTT broker or other pub/sub providers, such as an Apache Kafka broker. In this case, applications retrieve the data directly from the broker instead of using the API. A binary replacement for the JSON format are Protocol Buffers. They can be used with standard HTTP or the optimized gRPC protocol, which is based on HTTP/2 itself, but for certain technical reasons cannot be used in browser applications.

² <https://internationaldataspaces.org>

³ <https://gaia-x.eu/>

⁴ <https://bdva.eu/>

Whereas most HTTP APIs are based on the CRUD-paradigm ("Create, Read, Update, Delete") centred on individual entity operations, the GraphQL query language provides an alternative approach with native support for graph-structured data⁵.

Some frameworks for industrial IoT platforms provide generic, standardized APIs. The FIWARE initiative has developed the NGSI-LD specification, and the Asset Administration Shell also comes with a dedicated API specification. The proprietary IoT platforms also provide their own APIs.

4.2.5 Application runtimes

Environments for running heterogeneous applications should ideally support different kinds of programming languages natively and provide a flexible infrastructure allowing for simple addition and removal of capacities. The Kubernetes platform as a container orchestration tool is a very widespread option but comes with some administration overhead.

Another common tool in the data-science community is Apache Spark; it is more limited in the choice of programming language support, including Python, Scala/Java and R as options, but providing many useful abstractions for the processing of large datasets. It allows for the distributed execution of data processing pipelines.

Besides the runtime itself, for machine learning applications it is useful to have a model repository, providing among others versioning and lifecycle management. The mlflow tool is a convenient open-source solution for this purpose. It also allows to execute models as Spark applications or Docker containers and to track results.

4.2.6 Semantic models

Semantic models provide metadata describing the structure and meaning of the actual data in the platform. They are usually an integral part of the API descriptions and aimed at enabling semantic interoperability. These models must be machine-readable and adhere to a specific metamodel. Some common choices for representing semantic models include RDF, the Resource Description Framework, which can be serialized as XML, JSON-LD or Turtle, among others, and JSON schema. The latter is the basis for the API documentation standard OpenAPI and is therefore well suited for integration with HTTP APIs. It should be noted that there is also a dedicated query language for RDF, called SPARQL, which is usually transmitted via HTTP, as well.

FIWARE adopts a modelling approach based on a metamodel and a cross-domain ontology, which can be mapped to RDF. The Smart Data Models initiative is an offshoot that defines compatible domain-specific models for various application domains. Likewise, OPC-UA defines a set of companion specifications of domain-specific information models, for instance for pumps or for machine vision. In the case of the Asset Administration Shell initiative the corresponding concept is that of submodels. The Azure digital twins platform supports the Digital Twin Definition Language (DTDL) as its metamodel and suggests the use of sector specific ontologies as a basis for custom models.

The standard IEC62264/ISA95 defines general purpose terminology for enterprise control systems. The Smart Applications REference (SAREF) ontologies published by ETSI form a

⁵ <https://graphql.org/>

set of models for the IoT, including the SAREF for industry and manufacturing model (SAREF4INMA).

There does not seem to exist any authoritative ontology for the pulp and paper industry. The model used in an older research project KNOWMOBILE of VTT and Åbo University has been published in a VTT working paper⁶. Its material submodel is shown in Figure 16, and the decomposition of the paper making line in Figure 17.

Figure 16. Material submodel from VTT working paper 153.

Figure 17. Model of a paper making line from VTT working paper 153.

4.2.7 User interaction

An important part of an IoT platform are the user interfaces. They usually include at least some graphical interfaces (GUIs), typically in the form of web applications accessible via a web browser, and possibly others, such as alarming channels via SMS, E-Mail or mobile messengers. Augmented reality interfaces represent another more advanced form of potential interactions.

⁶ <https://publications.vtt.fi/pdf/workingpapers/2010/W153.pdf>

On the level of GUIs, the visualization of the current and past system state is the most basic requirement that has to be addressed. Open-source dashboarding tools such as Grafana⁷ or Apache Superset⁸ are common choices here. Both Grafana and Superset integrate some alarming mechanisms, as well. More advanced visualizations and decision support systems are better realized as dedicated web apps.

4.2.8 Digital Twins

The concept of Digital Twins is used to describe digital representations of physical assets. In an industrial context, Digital Twins are often created for machines or (semi-)products. They can encompass several different aspects, such as a data mirror (sometimes called a digital shadow), simulation models, construction drawings, 2D or 3D visualizations, etc. The Digital Twin Consortium has developed a *Digital Twin Capabilities Periodic Table*, which visualizes a large set of high-level capabilities assigned to digital twins, see Figure 18.

Figure 18. Digital Twin Capabilities Periodic Table (source: Digital Twin Consortium)

In the case of SteamDry the data connectivity and simulation aspects of Digital Twins will be used and applied to the equipment units, such as dryer, cleaner, heat exchanger, compressor, etc., as well as the paper web.

A common challenge in the generation of product Digital Twins in process industry is the need to process material tracing information in order to convert time-based process data to position-based product data.

4.2.9 Information Security

Information Security for IoT applications is of particular importance due to the direct impact incidents can have on the operational technology. Safeguarding the network is a multi-faceted undertaking, which should include technical measures such as network segmentation, transport encryption, authentication and authorization for software components, system monitoring, etc. The NIST Guide to Operational Technology (OT) Security⁹ is an excellent resource providing recommendations on how to approach this topic.

⁷ <https://grafana.com/>
⁸ <https://superset.apache.org/>
⁹ <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.800-82r3>

On the software development side, the use of automated tests, secure coding guidelines and regular security reviews are tools that can support the achievement of an appropriate level of information security. Guidelines published by the OWASP foundation¹⁰, for instance for web application security or mobile app security, help focus on the most relevant vulnerabilities.

4.3 Platforms

Several existing software platforms provide many of the above-mentioned capabilities off the shelf. Both commercial and open-source platforms exist, and there are at least two relevant standardisation activities, the NGSI-LD series of ETSI standards for context information management¹¹, grown out of the FIWARE initiative, and the Asset Administration Shell (AAS), maintained by the Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA)¹². Focus of the former seems to be mostly on Smart Cities applications, whereas the latter is actually manufacturing driven. There are open-source implementations of both NGSI-LD and the AAS¹³.

While the use of open standards and open-source software is certainly attractive for a research project, the mentioned standards are in an early phase of development, and they appear significantly less mature than the commercial platforms. For instance, in a preprint based on experiences from the CAPRI project (cf. Section 4.4.1 below)¹⁴, the feature completeness of several IoT platforms and specifications regarding timeseries-related APIs has been investigated, and it was found that NGSI-LD and AAS lagged behind the leading proprietary platforms.

4.4 European research projects

In the following subsections, the software architecture from two previous European research projects is presented.

4.4.1 CAPRI

The CAPRI project developed a software platform for process industries, which has been showcased in three applications in the asphalt, steel and pharma industries. It is based on the FIWARE platform. Figure 19 shows the conceptual architecture and Figure 20 shows the open-source software components used for the implementation. The FIWARE context broker (Orion) is at the core of the platform, and Apache Spark is used for data processing. For the visualization layer the dashboarding tools Grafana and Apache Superset have been used, the figure is slightly outdated in this respect.

¹⁰ <https://owasp.org>

¹¹ <https://www.etsi.org/committee/cim>

¹² <https://industrialdigitaltwin.org/>

¹³ See [https://github.com/FIWARE/catalogue/tree/master/core#ngsi-ld-context-broker-
implementations](https://github.com/FIWARE/catalogue/tree/master/core#ngsi-ld-context-broker-implementations) for an overview of NGSI-LD broker implementations and <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23115229> for the AAS.

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2310.03761>

Figure 19. CAPRI Edge-Cloud reference architecture (from CAPRI D3.1: Final reference architecture)

Figure 20. CAPRI reference implementation (from CAPRI D3.1: Final reference architecture)

4.4.2 COCOP Project

The COCOP project (Coordinating Optimisation of Complex Industrial Processes) dealt with plant-wide monitoring and control of complex distributed processes in the copper and steel industries. Its software architecture emphasizes the loose coupling aspect between components, based on a message bus. See Figure 21 for an overview of the system architecture.

Figure 21. COCOP decoupled software architecture (from: COCOP D3.7: Software architecture description for the runtime system)

The central communication bus has been realized in terms of the AMQP protocol, which implements the publish-subscribe messaging pattern.

4.5 Automation in the paper and pulp industry

Automation development has helped the pulp and paper industry, especially by enhancing efficiency, quality control, and energy management. In process optimization the automation helps to control material flow, monitor production parameters and make real-time adjustments, leading to increased efficiency and reduced waste. This improves quality control when using advanced sensors and monitoring tools that within automation systems can detect variations in raw materials and adjust processing parameters to ensure consistent product quality. In addition, energy efficiency is improved, especially by adjusting processes based on real-time energy demand which reduces operational costs. The real-time monitoring can be used to predict failures and reduce downtime, increasing reliability and thus productivity.¹⁵

Automation use in data analytics and decision support systems helps to provide better insights, improving throughput and yield by estimated amount of 5-10%.¹⁶

Automation today is used to provide a holistic view on the complex production system where distributed control systems, control and optimisation, analysers and measurements together provide tools for quality management. With these connected solutions automation is used in personnel training, maintenance, technical support, condition monitoring, among others.¹⁷

¹⁵ <https://www.pulpandpaper-technology.com/articles/pulp-and-paper-automation-improving-productivity-and-reliability>

¹⁶ <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/packaging-and-paper/our-insights/tapping-digital-full-potential-in-pulp-and-paper-process-optimization>

¹⁷ <https://www.valmet.com/automation/pulp/>

5 SteamDry IT concept

The SteamDry IT concept provides solutions for the monitoring and control of the pilot plant (cf. Section 3) as well as the data exchange required for the modelling activities (cf. Section 2).

5.1 Model development

The models developed in work packages 3-7 and 11 are operated individually by the responsible partners and do not need any coordination, except for the offline exchange of input and output data. Most of the models require a proprietary runtime platform and cannot easily be integrated into a common environment. There are significant dependencies regarding the datasets, however, as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2. For instance, the dynamic SSD process model from WP4, which is updated in WP5, will include a surrogate model for the cleaning process, developed in WP7, and itself generates data that will be used for building the dryer digital twin in WP8. Therefore, the IT concept is concerned only with the data exchange between the model owners.

The online-capable digital twins and control algorithms developed in WP8 will be covered in Section 5.2 on the pilot plant below.

5.1.1 Data collection & exchange

A platform for the exchange of large datasets will be defined. Initially, MS SharePoint will be used for this purpose. If it turns out to be insufficient, other options will be evaluated and a more scalable solution will be agreed upon.

5.2 Pilot plant operation

The existing automation infrastructure for the pilot plant has been described in Section 3, and it will not be modified for SteamDry purposes, except for the integration of the new pilot dryer. In parallel to this existing infrastructure, a SteamDry data platform will be established, which collects all the relevant monitoring data and to which the digital twins and control software to be developed in the project will connect.

5.2.1 Data collection

Monitoring data from the automation system will be exported to the SteamDry data platform, initially by means of CSV file exports performed manually and later through an automated solution. During trial runs, we aim to collect sensor data at 10 s resolution, which will lead to an estimated volume of less than 1 GB/day.

5.2.2 Storage

The main data sources to be considered consist of sensors measuring quantities such as temperature, moisture, pressure, etc. Therefore, the efficient storage of timeseries data is of great importance, which will be realized through a dedicated timeseries database. In addition, asset-related information (digital twin data) needs to be stored in a structured database. Both classical relational databases and document-centric NoSQL databases are possible options, here.

On the timeseries side, two well-established databases are InfluxDB and TimescaleDB. Both provide an open-source version with somewhat limited functionality, and a free

community version with extended functionality but under a more restrictive license¹⁸. InfluxDB in addition has a commercial edition, whereas the commercial cloud offering of TimescaleDB seems to coincide with the community edition. For the SteamDry pilot case we expect either the open-source or free community editions to be sufficient. TimescaleDB is an extension to the popular relational database PostgreSQL. For both InfluxDB and TimescaleDB/PostgreSQL many integrations into 3rd party software packages and support tools are available. For instance, the open-source dashboarding tool Grafana provides data source connectors for both types of timeseries databases.

Another important development in the realm of timeseries storage is the increasing use of the Parquet file format²⁰, a standardized binary format for columnar data. Its advantages include the efficient use of storage space, fast columnar reading, the possibility to push filter conditions to the file reading level, and the standardized layout. Due to these advantages the current version of the InfluxDB database uses Parquet files for its long-term storage layer. However, although the source code of InfluxDB is openly available, at the time of writing this document, no binary executables of the latest edition are provided by the governing company, hindering the adoption of the Parquet-based InfluxDB version by research projects like SteamDry.

We thus propose to realize the storage layer of the SteamDry data platform by means of a PostgreSQL database with TimescaleDB extension (Figure 13). An important advantage of this approach is the use of a single database technology, which we anticipate will simplify the administration and integration tasks required for setting up and operating the platform. The use of InfluxDB as an alternative timeseries storage layer may be reconsidered in the future, however.

Figure 22. Proposed storage solutions for the data platform

5.2.3 Interfaces and authorization

The application programming interfaces (APIs) form the access point to the platform for applications, such as the digital twins and agents developed in WP8. They abstract away the low-level database interfaces of the underlying storage technology and provide a more developer-friendly way of interacting with the platform. APIs may also provide the

¹⁸ <https://www.influxdata.com/blog/the-plan-for-influxdb-3-0-open-source/>

¹⁹ <https://docs.timescale.com/about/latest/timescaledb-editions/>

²⁰ <https://parquet.apache.org/>

entry point for sensor data, although the initial integration method will rather be based on file import. The role of APIs in the SteamDry platform is illustrated in Figure 23.

Figure 23. Application programming interfaces as access points to the SteamDry platform.

Application-facing interfaces will be realized in terms of the standard HTTP protocol. In addition, the use of web sockets as a streaming extension of HTTP will be evaluated. For the southbound interface (connecting data sources) the use of an MQTT interface may be considered instead, depending on the capabilities of the pilot plant automation system.

Comprehensive and accessible documentation of the APIs is essential for successful application development. The well-established OpenAPI specification²¹ and Swagger documentation tool²² will be used for documenting the HTTP interfaces of the SteamDry platform. In case of streaming interfaces, the AsyncAPI²³ format will be employed.

A potential open-source component providing the envisioned APIs is the Nest.js²⁴ framework for the Node.js platform. It supports both HTTP, websockets and GraphQL interfaces and supports OpenAPI/Swagger documentation. Many similar frameworks exist, however, in almost every major programming language.

In order to guarantee the integrity and confidentiality of the data stored in the platform, appropriate authentication and authorization mechanisms must be implemented. In web-based applications the most relevant standards currently seem to be OpenIdConnect and OAuth 2.0, although there are several competing standards of relevance in the enterprise world. We propose the usage of Keycloak²⁵ as an open-source identity management (IdM) tool supporting the above-mentioned standards. The positioning of the IdM and its interaction with the APIs is illustrated in Figure 24.

²¹ <https://www.openapis.org>
²² <https://swagger.io>
²³ <https://www.asyncapi.com>
²⁴ <https://nestjs.com/>
²⁵ <https://keycloak.org>

Figure 24. Interaction of the API components with the identity management (IdM).

5.2.4 Digital Twins and Agents

The digital twins of process equipment and products, as well as the agents implementing the control algorithms need to interact with the data platform, for instance reading sensor data and updating setpoints. For this purpose, they make use of the interfaces described in the section above. Although it is foreseen at the time of writing to realize all the twins and agents in the Python programming language, the implementation of the platform will not be limited to this specific software. A common choice as a runtime for heterogenous software components is the container orchestration system Kubernetes²⁶, which we will adopt. A somewhat simpler alternative for single-machine deployments, particularly useful during the development phase, is the Docker Compose²⁷ software. We aim to provide a Compose configuration for the platform, as well, and if single-machine deployments of the complete platform turn out to be feasible we may decide to skip the Kubernetes deployment.

The flexibility of supporting generic containerized applications may also allow the direct integration of some of the models developed in WPs 3-7 as part of the digital twins, in case they can be operated in near-real time. The use of surrogate models in the digital twins is the foreseen mode of integration, however.

Since several different models will be implemented in the Python programming language, we envision the creation of a small software development kit (SDK) for this language, to avoid the need for repetitive implementations of the platform connector.

5.2.5 User Interface

The user interface will be realized in terms of web apps connecting to the platform via the APIs. The main user interface will provide a visualization for the operator, showing sensor data and KPIs about the pilot plant, as well as digital twin results and the state of the agent system. The open-source dashboarding software Grafana may be used to realize the monitoring frontend; it allows for the simple integration of custom data source

²⁶ <https://kubernetes.io>

²⁷ <https://docs.docker.com/compose>

connectors via a dedicated plugin interface²⁸. Besides the operator frontend an administration frontend may be required. Both of them will require the user to login prior to accessing any page. For this purpose, the frontends communicate with the same identity management system that is also used to secure the APIs, as shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25. Graphical user interfaces (GUIs) as access points for human users to the system.

The digital twin and agent components may provide additional frontends for user interaction, but this remains to be decided. Since these components are currently foreseen to be realized in Python, these frontends could be conveniently implemented with a Python frontend technology, such as Dash, or Jinja in combination with FastAPI.

5.2.6 Control concept

An innovative control algorithm for the superheated steam pilot will be realized in SteamDry, using an agent-based optimization system that can take into account multiple optimization targets simultaneously, such as energy minimization, moisture control and product quality optimization. During pilot trials, the algorithm will generate setpoints for different components impacting the steam circuit, such as the dryer, cleaner and heat exchanger. The system response to these different operating setpoints will then be fed back to the control system to enable the learning of optimum operating conditions.

In order to enable a smooth implementation of the first trials the initial version of the system will not be connected directly to the automation system of the pilot plant to adapt any device setpoints, instead the recommended setpoints will be displayed to the operator (via the operator GUI, see Figure 25), who can then decide whether to follow the recommendation, to adapt it, or to keep the current state. Among others, this alleviates the need to implement sophisticated safety measures for preventing hazardous system settings, leaving the plant operator responsible for ensuring safe conditions at all times. This approach is illustrated in Figure 26.

²⁸ <https://grafana.com/developers/plugin-tools/tutorials/build-a-data-source-plugin>

Figure 26. Initial control concept for the SteamDry pilot plant.

After the initial trials the partners involved will re-evaluate the option to establish a direct connectivity between the platform and the automation control layer. Figure 27 displays this potential setup.

Figure 27. Potential evolution of the control concept, allowing for direct control of the device setpoints.

5.2.7 Summary

We propose the development of a custom data platform for monitoring and control of the SteamDry pilot plant. This platform will exist side-by-side with the existing plant automation system, importing sensor data from the latter. The digital twins to be developed in WP8 retrieve their input data via the platform APIs and also write simulation results back via these APIs. The control concept foresees the visualization of setpoints determined by the agent-based controller to the plant operator who takes the final decision on new device setpoints.

It should be noted that the concept is kept deliberately simple at this point but will likely require adaptations to upcoming requirements during the project. For instance, the digital twins for the different plant components are currently foreseen as standalone software modules interacting exclusively with the platform via the APIs. If the platform needs to support coupled simulations of “what-if” scenarios, involving multiple twin components, then direct interactions between individual twin modules may become necessary. We will continue adapting the architecture as the project progresses.

The proposed architecture and software components involved are shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28. Overview of the SteamDry data platform and application platform with proposed software modules and transport protocols.

6 Conclusion

The present document has introduced the software modules that will be implemented in the SteamDry project to support the development of superheated steam drying technology for the pulp and paper industry. Furthermore, it has established the state of the art for Industrial IoT platforms and proposed an IT concept for the implementation in SteamDry. The concept should be thought of as a starting point since it will certainly need to evolve with the progress of the project.